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Review Article

A Review On Role Of Artificial Intelligence In Drug Development

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ABSTRACT

Background:

This abstract explores the pivotal role of artificial intelligence (AI) in revolutionizing drug development processes. Analysing vast datasets, AI facilitates target identification, drug screening, and prediction of compound interactions, expediting the discovery of novel therapeutics. The integration of AI technologies marks a transformative era in drug development, offering unprecedented opportunities for innovation and improved patient outcomes. In this review, we delve into the dynamic landscape of artificial intelligence (AI) within the realm of drug development. Our exploration encompasses a thorough examination of recent literature, dissecting how AI accelerates drug discovery, refines clinical trial processes, and propels personalized medicine initiatives. Additionally, we project into the future, unravelling potential implications that AI holds for the evolving landscape of drug development.

Main body of the abstract:

This review delves into AI-powered approaches, such as machine learning and deep learning GNNs, CNNs, DNNs showcasing their impact on optimizing drug design, minimizing development timelines, and enhancing overall efficiency in the pharmaceutical industry. By scrutinizing challenges and limitations, we elucidate the nuanced interplay between AI and pharmaceutical innovation.

Short conclusion:

AI in drug development has shown great promise in revolutionizing the pharmaceutical industry. By utilizing large datasets and advanced algorithms, AI can assist in predicting outcomes and identifying potential drug candidates. This review serves as a comprehensive guide for researchers, practitioners, and stakeholders navigating the complex and promising intersection of AI and pharmaceuticals.

INTRODUCTION

Main text: Artificial Intelligence (AI), denotes the replication of human intelligence in machines that

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are programmed to cogitate and acquire knowledge akin to humans. It encompasses a broad spectrum of technologies and methodologies that enable computers and software to execute tasks that conventionally necessitate human intelligence. The procedure encompasses the procurement of information, the formulation of guidelines for utilizing said information, the derivation of approximate or definitive inferences, and the act of self-correction.¹ Artificial intelligence (AI) employs personified expertise and assimilates insights from the outcomes it generates to tackle not only specific quandaries but also intricate predicaments. Remarkable enhancements in computational process, coupled with advancements in AI technology, hold the potential to revolutionize the process of drug development. AI harnesses systems and software capable of comprehending and assimilating the input data to autonomously and reliably make decisions in order to achieve predetermined objectives.² The existence of artificial intelligence is contingent upon human intelligence, as humans are the architects behind its creation; hence, it does not pose a complete replacement for human physical presence.³ In the present era, the pharmaceutical industry confronts challenges in sustaining their drug development endeavors due to escalated research and development expenses and diminished efficiency.⁴ Temporal consumption and production costs represent the primary concerns in drug development. Furthermore, inefficiency, imprecise target delivery, and suboptimal dosages pose additional obstacles that impede the progress of drug development.⁵ The pharmaceutical industry could undergo a profound transformation if artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are effectively employed in drug research. These tools

possess the capability to expedite the discovery of innovative medicinal compounds, prognosticate their effectiveness and toxicity, and enhance medication design. Over the past few years, the pharmaceutical sector has witnessed a substantial surge in data digitalization. Nevertheless, this digitalization engenders the challenge of acquiring, analysing, and applying the acquired knowledge to unravel intricate clinical predicaments. This serves as the impetus for the adoption of AI, as it is endowed with the ability to process copious amounts of data with heightened automation.⁶ AI encompasses various methodological domains, including reasoning, knowledge representation, solution search, with machine learning (ML) constituting a cardinal paradigm among them.

Advantages of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in pharmaceutical development:

Accelerated drug development:

With the emergence of AI, the process of target identification can be expedited through the utilization of machine learning algorithms to analyse vast datasets. For instance, a machine learning algorithm can aid in the analysis of extensive genomic data pertaining to a particular disease, enabling the identification of potential drug targets and the prediction of drug efficacy. Furthermore, machine learning algorithms can also examine scientific literature to pinpoint potential drug targets and facilitate the identification of genetic biomarkers for disease diagnosis and prognosis.⁷

Continuous progression:

In addition to assisting humans with mundane tasks, AI harnesses the latest advancements in biology and computing. This evolutionary process, coupled with the continuous enhancement of innovative capabilities and the reduction of costs

associated with AI tools, assumes a pivotal role in driving advancements in drug development, both presently and in the future.

Optimization of processes and scale-up:

AI models that leverage machine learning techniques can utilize process development data to expedite the design process and identify optimal process parameters or scale-up strategies, thereby reducing the duration of development and minimizing waste.⁸

Enhanced predictability:

In the realm of drug screenings, the utilization of robust AI tools significantly enhances the predictability of the process of delineating meaningful interactions. Consequently, a meticulous and comprehensive approach to the design of parameters can effectively diminish the occurrence of false positives.

Process control:

Advanced process control techniques have the potential to enable dynamic control over manufacturing processes, thereby enabling the development of process controls that can accurately forecast the trajectory of a given process, in conjunction with real-time sensor data. Pharmaceutical manufacturers are poised to embrace advanced process control methodologies that merge AI techniques with knowledge of chemistry and physics, in order to optimize manufacturing efficiency and output.⁹

Process monitoring and fault detection:

AI methodologies can be harnessed to effectively monitor equipment and identify deviations from optimal performance. Detected deviations can then trigger maintenance activities in a manner that minimizes process downtime.

Trend monitoring:

Integration of AI methodologies with process performance metrics can offer enhanced trend

monitoring capabilities, even when considering multiple products or geographical locations. Consequently, proactive corrective and preventive actions can be executed to mitigate the potential impact on the supply chain or avert drug shortages.¹⁰

Data analysis in clinical trials:

One notable benefit of AI technology in the context of clinical trials is the ability to conduct more accurate data analysis. AI algorithms are capable of swiftly and accurately analyzing large datasets, surpassing the capabilities of humans. This enables researchers to identify intricate patterns and correlations that would otherwise be challenging to discern, thereby facilitating the generation of novel insights and discoveries. AI can also assist researchers in making well-informed decisions pertaining to trial design, patient selection, and progress monitoring.¹²

Personalized Treatment:

AI can contribute to the prediction of patient responses to drugs, thus paving the way for personalized medicine that tailors treatment plans to the unique characteristics of individual patients.

Disadvantages of AI:

at present, the realm of synthetic intelligence (AI) has observed notable progress, garnered extensive interest, and propelled innovation throughout diverse sectors. Nevertheless, amidst this advancement, it is imperative to recognize that the path towards AI integration is not devoid of its obstacles. These hurdles in artificial intelligences encompass a plethora of intricacies that necessitate meticulous deliberation and strategic approaches. In the subsequent section, we shall probe into the multifaceted terrain of AI challenges, delving into the complexities that hinder the widespread adoption and seamless implementation of AI systems.

Lack of understanding:

AI is still very new field, and there is much we have yet to comprehend about its inner workings. This lack of understanding can impede the development of reliable and accurate AI systems. To address these challenges in artificial intelligence, companies can invest in research and development efforts to advance the understanding of AI algorithms, model, and techniques.¹³

Privacy concerns:

AI systems often rely on vast amount of data to train and operate effectively. However, this data can include personal and sensitive information, leading to concerns regarding privacy and data protection. To litigate these concerns, companies or industries must prioritize implementing robust privacy measures, such as data anonymization, secure data storage, and compliance with relevant data storage, and regulations. Transparent data usage policies and obtaining informed consent from individuals can also enhance trust and alleviate privacy concerns. Processing power requirements: AI systems can be computationally demanding, requiring substantial processing power to perform complex tasks. This can result in high-infrastructure costs, especially for resource-intensive AI applications. To overcome these challenges in artificial intelligence, companies can leverage advancements in hardware technology, such as specialized AI chips and distributed computing systems. Cloud computing services also provide scalable and cost-effective solutions for accessing the necessary computational resources.¹⁴

Lack of data:

AI systems heavily depends on large and diverse datasets for training and achieving optimal performance. However, not all industries have access to the required volume or quality of data.

Companies can address these challenges in artificial intelligence by fostering collaborations and partnerships to gain access to relevant datasets. Furthermore, techniques like transfer learning, data augmentation, and synthetic data generation can help mitigate the issue of limited data availability.

Implementation strategy:

There is no one-size-fits-all approach to implementing AI. Each industry has unique requirements, and effective implementation strategy should be tailored to its specific needs. It is essential to conduct thorough assessments of existing infrastructure, data availability, and organizational readiness. Industries should formulate a clear road map that outlines the steps, resources, and timelines required for successful AI integration, collaborating with AI experts and seeing external guidance can also provide valuable insights during the implementation process.¹⁵

AI models utilized in pharmaceutical development:

In the realm of pharmaceutical product advancement, diverse AI models have been investigated to enhance various facets of the procedure. The development of medications is a protracted and costly endeavor. The repurposing of existing drugs for new therapies presents an appealing solution that expedites the process while reducing experimental expenses. AI/ML techniques possess the potential to augment the probability of success in drug development by engendering significant enhancements in multiple sectors of research and development, encompassing: the identification of innovative targets, comprehension of target-disease associations, selection of drug candidates, prognostication of protein structures, design and optimization of molecular compounds,

understanding of disease mechanisms, development of novel prognostic and predictive biomarkers, analysis of biometric data derived from wearable devices, imaging, precision medicine, and more recently, the design, execution, and analysis of clinical trials. Within this context, AI techniques primarily encompass machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL). Both ML and DL algorithms are utilized in the discovery and validation of targets, the discovery and design of drugs, and preclinical drug research, wherein they are deployed to scrutinize diverse data characteristics presented in various formats.¹⁵ Following the enrollment of a drug candidate in a clinical trial, DL assumes a vital role in facilitating the design of the trial, as well as supervising and analysing data derived from the clinical phase IV. AI technologies are employed in both drug screening and drug design; the algorithm comprises, among others, ML, deep learning, AI-based quantitative structure- activity relationship (QSAR) technologies, QSLRML, virtual screening (VS), support vector machines (SVMs), deep virtual screening, deep neural networks (DNNs), recurrent neural networks (RNNs), etc.¹⁶

Supervised Learning:

supervised learning alludes to a form of machine learning in which an algorithm is educated on a labelled dataset, where the desired output is already acknowledged. The algorithm acquires the ability to map input data to the accurate output by scrutinizing the patterns and relationships within the labelled data. This methodology is frequently employed in a myriad of applications such as image recognition, natural language processing, and predictive modelling. Task-oriented strategies encompass the establishment of explicit objectives aimed at attaining desired outcomes from a given set of inputs. This approach harnesses labelled data

to train algorithms for tasks such as data classification or outcomes forecasting. The dominant supervised learning tasks encompass classification, which entails predicting a label, and regression, which entails predicting a quantity. A diverse range of techniques are at one's disposal for solving supervised learning tasks, contingent upon the nature of the data given the problem domain. Supervised machine learning encompasses a myriad of algorithms such as:

1. Classification:

- Naïve Bayes classifier
- K-nearest neighbours
- Support vector machines
- Ensemble learning

2. Regression:

- Neural networks
- Decision trees
- Linear regression
- Support vector regression
- Polynomial regression¹⁷

Unsupervised Learning: whereas supervised learning methods are employed to prognosticate the forthcoming values of data classified, unsupervised learning methods are employed predominantly for exploratory intentions. Unsupervised learning formulates a model which encompasses solely inputs. In this form of erudition, output is not extant and the unlabelled data is utilized in this learning. Unsupervised learning is more intricate and it performs real-time scrutiny. It furnishes moderate yet dependable output. Unsupervised learning is employed in manifold applications such as clientele segmentation, depict compression, and trait extraction.

Instances of clustering learning:

- Gaussian mixture

- Hidden Markov model
- K-means clustering,
- Principal component analysis¹⁸

Reinforcement learning:

It pertains to the process in which an algorithm acquires knowledge through active engagement with its surroundings, whereby it is bestowed with feedback in the manner of both rewards and penalties. Subsequently, the algorithm adeptly adapts its actions in order to optimize the overall accumulation of rewards. This particular methodology finds frequent employment in domains such as robotics and autonomous vehicles.¹⁹

Machine learning:

Machine learning techniques have found applications in the field of computer assisted drug discovery. These algorithms are commonly employed to tackle practical problems. There are instances where machine learning has been successfully utilized in medicine particularly in medical imaging, astronomy, computational biology, agriculture and the pharmaceutical industry. It is worth noting that machine learning plays a role in contemporary research, on natural language processing. Machine learning approaches can be classified into categories based on their learning methods and intended purposes. These include:

- supervised learning,
- unsupervised or cluster-based learning,
- dimensionality reduction techniques
- semi supervised learning methods
- reinforcement learning strategies
- deep learning methodologies.²⁰

Dimensionality reduction:

it involves transforming data from a dimensional representation to a lower dimensional one. As the

amount of data stored on disk drives (HDD) continues to grow the use of various dimensionality reduction techniques has become widespread in many fields of application. Furthermore new techniques are constantly emerging. Dimensionality reduction methods (DRTs) take a dataset with high dimensionality and convert it into a new dataset that represents lower dimensionality while preserving the original meaning of the data as much, as possible. DRTs can be employed to extract the relevant features necessary for analysis while eliminating redundant and unnecessary ones. By utilizing DRTs, time and storage space requirements can be reduced.²¹

Deep learning:

In essence, deep learning is a subset of machine learning and involves neural networks with three or more layers. By emulating brain activity, these neural networks enable the human brain to "learn" from massive amounts of data. Additional hidden layers can help optimize and adjust for accuracy, even if a single-layer neural network can still make rough predictions. Many applications and services for artificial intelligence (AI) rely on deep learning to improve automation by performing physical and analytical tasks without human interaction. Deep learning differs from traditional machine learning techniques in its ability to learn complex relationships between input features and output decisions from large-scale data, aided by the continuous increase of computing power from hardware equipment. In particular, deep learning methods can automatically learn multiple levels of representations using only its input data, without the need of additional user input. Although their use in drug repurposing is still in its infancy, they have already demonstrated.²²

Deep neural networks:

A feed-forward neural network with densely coupled input, hidden, and output layers is called a deep neural network (DDN). With different neurons in each layer, it simulates nonlinear transitions between neurons to produce the properties of learning input data.

Convolutional neural network (CNN): Convolutional layers, which extract features, and pooling layers, which reduce dimensionality, make up a CNN, which is a feed-forward neural network. Convolutional and pooling layers facilitate the extraction of all the data from a dataset with little computing overhead.

Recurrent neural network (RNN):

A RNN is a type of artificial neural network (ANN) wherein a temporal sequence's connected nodes create an undirected or directed graph. A feedback component in an RNN enables signals from one layer to be relayed back into the layer before it. Since it is the only neural network with internal memory, it can help with the challenge of learning and retaining large amounts of information.

Graph neural network (GNN):

A GNN is a connective model that uses information exchanged between network nodes to determine a graph's relationships. A GNN may change a node's state based on its neighbours at any depth from the node; this state can be used to represent node information.

An autoencoder (AE):

It is a device that learns effective encodings of input data. It is composed of an encoder and a decoder. The encoder creates the encoding, which is then fed to the decoder, which regenerates the input. An AE frequently serves as a tool for dimensionality reduction and data compression using representation techniques (i.e., encoding) of a set of data.

Generative adversarial network (GAN):

The generator neural network and the discriminator neural network are the two basic neural networks that make up a generative adversarial network, or GAN. While the latter is used to differentiate the created material, the former is utilized to generate content. Additionally, models may be combined to handle a greater variety of issues. A graph convolution network (GCN), for instance, enables convolutional operations on graph data in addition to standard data (like pictures).²¹

Application of AI in drug development:

AI In Drug discovery:

In the drug discovery process, the development of novel drugs with the potential interactions therapeutic targets is of central importance. De novo drug design, which involves creating new molecules with specific pharmaceutical properties from the initial stages, is regarded as one of the most difficult computer-assisted drug discovery tasks because of the large cardinality of the chemical space containing drug-like molecules (roughly 10⁶⁰–10¹⁰⁰). While scoring functions carry out binding assays, chemical compound creation by computational approaches can be connected to imitation of synthetic chemistry. The scoring function is one of the assessment instruments used in the critical evaluation of candidates, which is essential for the design process. Multi-objective drug design takes into account numerous aspects simultaneously and can use various scoring methods in tandem. There are two possible approaches for de novo drug design:

- i. ligand-based and
- ii. receptor-based de novo drug design.

The latter strategy is more common. Since acceptable small molecules are built by fitting the fragments into the binding cavity of the receptors,

the quality of target protein structures and precise information about its binding location are crucial for receptor-based design. A computer program or co-crystallization of the ligand and receptor might be used to accomplish this. There are two methods for creating a receptor-based design: either starting with a single unit and generating a ligand from it, or starting with building blocks, which are atoms or fragments such as single rings, amines, and hydrocarbons that are joined to make a whole chemical molecule. The binding site is found using the fragment-linking approach in order to map the likely locations of interaction for the various functional groups that are present in the fragments. By joining these functional groups, an absolute compound is created. To create new compounds, fragment-based de novo design makes use of the entire chemical space. The choice of linkers is crucial when using the linking strategy. There are two methods for doing fragment anchoring at the binding site: (i) the outside-in approach and (ii) the inside-out technique. With the first method, the binding site develops inward and the building outward components are mostly positioned there. Building blocks are haphazardly inserted into the binding site and constructed via the inside-out technique.²² Predicting 3D structure of target protein: Since proteins are the body's molecular machinery and malfunctioning may lead to illnesses, finding new drugs that target proteins is essential. A protein's biological activity is determined by its three-dimensional structure, while substrates, cofactors, and protein binding are determined by the protein's conformational state. Engineered tiny molecules are used in rational drug delivery to selectively interact with proteins and modify their activity. Understanding the protein structure and all of its unique conformations is essential for designing small

molecules and for targeting proteins with precision. Regrettably, the three-dimensional structure of many proteins that are important for drug development has not yet been determined by experimentation. As a result, one of the hardest things to do is correctly anticipate their structure from their amino acid sequence. Recently, machine learning apps based on deep neural networks, such as RaptorX, trRosetta, AlphaFold, and AlphaFold2, have been able to predict unknown protein structures with previously unheard-of precision. About 35 percent of the more than 214 million predictions are considered extremely accurate by EMBL-EBI, meaning they match the quality of structures found through experimentation. Forty-five percent more were thought to be trustworthy enough for several applications. An end-to-end deep learning system would be taught as a single integrated structure with a system of sub-networks coupled together, in contrast to the numerous modules seen in the prior techniques, each of which was learned independently despite utilizing DL. In this sense, the end-to-end DL methods map to protein structures end- to-end using sequence as an input.

Predicting drug-protein interaction:

prediction of drug-protein interactions, or DPIs, is essential to the research and design of new drugs. Even while experimental tests are still the most trustworthy method for identifying DPIs, the high cost and time involved in conducting trials make it difficult to characterize every potential drug-protein combination. Finding new drug-protein interactions is essential to the drug discovery process. Numerous machine learning-based techniques have been created for this aim using one-dimensional (1D) protein sequences and pharmacological descriptors. Protein sequence,

however, is unable to sufficiently capture the interactions in three dimensions. However, because of the sparse 3D matrix and the small number of co-crystal structures that are accessible for training, a direct input of a 3D structure is inefficient. An end-to-end deep learning system that uses the visual question answering mode to describe pharmaceuticals with molecular linear notation (string) and proteins with 2D distance map from monomer structures (pictures) to predict interactions. We implemented a self-attentional sequential model to automatically extract semantic features from the linear notations and a dynamic attentive convolutional neural network to learn fixed-size representations from the variable-length distance maps in order to optimize the training of the systems.²⁴

Prediction of protein folding from sequence:

Protein dysfunctions are linked to the majority of clinical diseases. For this reason, knowledge of the structural features of proteins is essential to the SBDD method. It may be applied to determine which compounds are possibly active against the medication target proteins. It will be time-consuming and economical to predict and measure each protein target's 3D structure using in vitro methods. Therefore, it is highly commendable that suitable algorithms are now being developed for predicting the model structure of a protein. Even with the availability of the protein sequence, it remains an unsolvable issue to anticipate precise de novo prediction of related three-dimensional structures. Owing to the enhanced characteristics, topological information, backbone torsion angle, residue contacts and secondary structure prediction are all done using deep learning approaches. Additionally, one-dimensional and two-dimensional structures were combined using DL techniques, and residue-wise interactions were

predicted using CNN. It is still a goal to correctly forecast the 3D structure, and DL highlights future progress with its enhanced feature that can accurately explore the relationship between the sequence and structure of the protein via feature extraction technique. The 3D structure of target proteins is generally predicted using homology modeling and de novo techniques, which have grown increasingly precise and advanced over time. Nonetheless, the most current assessment of protein structure using AI technologies is designed and carried out to forecast the protein's three-dimensional structure. For example, an AI tool AlphaFold is used for the 3D structure of target protein, which accurately predicts about 25 structures from 45 structures.²⁵

AI in poly-pharmacology:

The purposeful creation of pharmacological compounds with the rare capacity to interact with several targets or pathways within an area of illness-related molecular networks is known as poly-pharmacology (simply the term "single disease multiple targets"). medical treatments that are both much more effective and less dangerous than standard therapies can be developed with this strategy. Among the well-known databases that include details on chemical pathways, binding affinities, pharmacological targets, and biological activities are PubChem, ChEMBL, DrugBank, and BindingDB. The AI system may utilize this data to recognize all medications that are currently on the market and to selectively irradiate them. The development of AI technology has the potential to revolutionize the drug development process due to its progress, processing power increase, and range of possible applications.²⁶

Designing multitarget drug molecules:

multispecific biotherapeutic medications are defined as therapeutic compounds based on

proteins that have the ability to bind to numerous pharmacological targets at once. These biomolecules can take the shape of antibodies, various antigen-binding fragment forms, tiny scaffold protein domains, peptides, enzymatic domains, protein receptors, chemicals, or oligonucleotides such as small interference RNA (siRNA) or anti-sense RNA. These biological components come together to produce a single molecule that has several therapeutic mechanisms of action because to their covalent bond.²⁷

AI in chemical synthesis:

Using DL and ML systems to forecast the results of chemical processes. Typically, these devices employ statistical learning techniques such as response type classification and automatic reaction center identification. The majority of DL techniques in retrosynthesis analysis follow similar guidelines; the main distinction is in the molecular representations that are employed. A simple molecular input line profile format (SMILES) string describing a product is converted into a SMILES string identifying a reactant using a sequence-to-sequence structure created by Liu et al. Using rule-based methods, an LSTM network was trained on 50,000 replies from US patents to attain parity.^() In order to increase the prediction accuracy of retrosynthesis, computer scientists have more recently used molecules as heterogeneous graphs and created graph neural networks (GNNs).²⁸

Prediction of retrosynthesis pathways:

Retrosynthetic analysis is the technique of employing chemical processes to create disconnections that will allow a target molecule to be broken down into intermediates and purchasable precursors. Historically, an expert chemist has handled this work, relying on their understanding of chemical processes to guide their

method. A database of 600 chemical transformations was employed for the early LHASA program to aid in the construction of potential pathways. Substructure matching to the reaction core and pertinent chemical context allows the transformation rules or templates to be applied to new molecules. When Segler et al. employed deep learning and then game AI in 2017 to quickly and effectively identify feasible pathways, the field saw a surge in interest. A database of known reactions was automatically translated into reaction and the nearest neighbor atoms rather than the rules having to be explicitly encoded. Through training to identify which template corresponded with a particular product, an artificial neural network (ANN) immediately acquired retrosynthetic methods from the data. To filter the data and guard against indications of improbable chemical reactions, more ANNs were employed. The combinatorial character of the autonomous AI- based retrosynthesis planning is one of its primary problems. To rank the many retrosynthetic alternatives, it is essential to accurately anticipate the reaction results in a forward synthesis way at every stage of synthetic route design.²⁹

AI in drug screening:

AI can be used to anticipate protein-drug interactions, virtually test and improve molecules, and evaluate their bioactivities. Artificial intelligence can aid in virtual screening by creating predictive models that can recognise substances that have a high likelihood of binding to a target protein. Several kinds of data, including structural details, molecular descriptors, and known protein-ligand complexes, can be used to train these models. When developing a new medication, it is important to take into account the physico-chemical properties of the substance, including its solubility,

intrinsic permeability, degree of ionization, and partition coefficient (logP), as they may indirectly affect how a drug interacts with a target receptor family. AI can also be used to generate insights into drug reaction mechanisms and create effective routes for chemical synthesis, as well as, to discover potentially undesirable interactions with other molecules.³⁰

Prediction of drug ADME pattern and toxicity:

Throughout the drug development process, the prediction of toxicity (T) and absorption, distribution, metabolism, and excretion (ADME) features aids in the identification of promising drug candidates and promotes drug-likeness. A variety of AI-based techniques have been used in recent research to forecast ADMET features in an effort to lower the preclinical failure rate in the drug discovery sector. Using ADMET attributes created using SVM or Bayesian algorithms, the SwissADME online tool predicts physicochemical parameters, descriptors, and drug-likeness. AdmetSAR2.0, which has 47 predictive models, and the AdmetSAR web server, which has 27 predictive models, were created. The gathered dataset was built using RF, SVM, and kNN models, and represented as chemical fingerprints. The variable closest neighbor (vNN) approach was created in a different research as an addition to the kNN method. Using vNN, fifteen prediction models were created and put into use in the vNN-ADMET web server [76]. An open-source software pipeline called ATOM Modeling PipeLine was developed to create prediction models [77]. It includes data curation, analysis, visualization, and model tweaking and training. In terms of data curation, the module contained DeepChem, Mordred, and the Molecular Operating Environment in addition to the RDKit and MolVS packages. To build new models, the

RF, XGBoost, NN, and GCNN approaches may be applied and supported on a variety of datasets. Large amounts of high-quality data are needed to provide reliable prediction results since the quality of the prediction model depends on the input data. Through a combination of algorithmic development and extensive database and benchmark building, drug discovery professionals will be able to use AI-based modelling to predict ADMET characteristics more accurately.³¹

AI in drug repurposing:

The process of employing an already-approved medication or medication candidate for a novel medical ailment or therapy for which it was not previously recommended is known as "drug repurposing." It was first created to address a distinct medical issue. Without specifically identifying the mechanism of action, repurposing can help discover novel drugs based on their phenotypic advantages. Preclinical animal models may be used to evaluate this directly, and research and clinical applications can benefit more from these findings. With repurposed medications, there is very little chance of failure. This method often makes use of open-access medication databases. Included are data from clinical studies, anecdotal stories on off-label usage, primary and translational research, and other publicly accessible human data. Researchers employ various bioinformatics techniques and artificial intelligence algorithms to methodically attempt to determine how medications interact with protein targets. One of the most potent applications of in-silico medication repositioning is its speed and cost-effectiveness.³² Molecular docking and machine learning are two important techniques for in silico repositioning. (1) In computer-assisted drug development and structural molecular biology, molecular docking techniques are used to

simulate and forecast the physical interactions that occur between drugs and targets. (2) Because machine learning techniques can analyse a larger number of possible candidates for future experimental screening, they often offer more benefits than docking simulation.³³

Clinical trial design and monitoring:

Over the past several decades, the application of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) in clinical settings has grown significantly; there are many instances in the fields of acute care, cardiology, and medical imaging. The success percentage of clinical trials at this time ranges from 10% to 13.8%.³⁴ Clinical trial conduct has several components, including protocol execution, patient selection, recruitment, monitoring, and retention, safety reporting compliance, and ongoing review and data analysis. In addition to its many other uses, Bayesian nonparametric models, or BNMs, have become a highly useful tool for designing clinical trials. This model applies a nanometric approach and is highly adaptable. This method reduces the amount of time needed for trial planning and clustering. Dirichlet process mixture models and Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) methods are two popular BNMs.³⁵ Benefits of leveraging AI in clinical trials: Faster time to market, reduced costs, more accurate data analysis, personalized medicine, improved patient outcome, real-time access to expertise, patient recruitment and screening, trial design and optimization, data collection and analysis, predictive modelling, adverse event detection and many more.³⁶

CONCLUSION

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a technology that simulates human intelligence in machines, enabling them to perform tasks typically required by humans. It can revolutionize the drug

development process by utilizing advanced computational power and machine learning techniques. AI can address complex problems such as time consumption, production cost, inefficiency, inaccurate target delivery, and inappropriate dosage. The pharmaceutical industry faces challenges in sustaining their drug development programs due to increased R&D costs and reduced efficiency. AI and machine learning can help accelerate drug development by analysing large data sets, identifying potential drug targets, and predicting drug effectiveness. AI also offers constant advancements in biology and computing, allowing for faster design and optimization of process parameters or scale-up strategies. Higher predictivity in drug screenings can reduce false positives, while advanced process control can improve manufacturing efficiency and output. AI methods can be used for better monitoring equipment and detecting changes in optimal performance, leading to proactive corrective and preventive actions. Data analysis in clinical trials allows for more accurate data analysis than humans, helping researchers identify patterns and correlations that would be difficult for humans to detect. This can lead to new insights and discoveries, and personalized treatment can be achieved by predicting patient responses to drugs. However, AI has its challenges. Companies must invest in research and development efforts to advance the understanding of AI algorithms, models, and techniques. Privacy concerns arise from the vast amounts of data used in AI systems, which can include personal and sensitive information. Companies should prioritize implementing robust privacy measures, such as data anonymization, secure data storage, and compliance with relevant data storage and regulations.

LIST OF ABBREVIATION:

NOT APPLICABLE

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